

The Effect of Twisting on the Capture and Release of Singlet Oxygen by Tethered Twisted Acenes

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Supporting Information Placeholder

ABSTRACT: The use of polyaromatic hydrocarbons to capture and release singlet oxygen is of considerable importance in materials chemistry, synthesis, and photodynamic therapy. Here, we studied the ability of a series of tethered twistacenes, possessing different degrees of backbone twist, to capture and release singlet oxygen via reversible Diels-Alder reaction. When the twistacene acts as both sensitizer and diene the photo-oxidation rate depends on the extinction coefficient as the irradiation wavelength. However, when the twistacenes function solely as a diene, the rate of photo-oxidation increases with increasing twist. The rate of the reverse reaction, the singlet oxygen release, increases with increasing twist. The calculated transition state is decreasing with increasing twist, which can explain the observed trend. The presence of the tether significantly increases the reversibility of the reaction, which can proceed in repeated forward and reverse cycles with very high yield under mild conditions, as required for molecular switches.

Singlet oxygen ($^1\text{O}_2$) is widely used in synthesis and in biological and materials science applications.^{1,2} Acenes can undergo oxygenation with $^1\text{O}_2$ to yield endoperoxides, which in turn can release $^1\text{O}_2$ and parent acene. This reversible capture and release of $^1\text{O}_2$ has been applied in lithographic applications, luminescent $^1\text{O}_2$ -response polymer design, oxygen storage, and molecular rotors.³⁻⁸ Consequently, the ability to predict acene reactivity toward oxygenation and the degree of reversibility of that reaction are of great importance. However, the factors that govern reactivity with respect to both the capture and release of $^1\text{O}_2$ from polyaromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) are not well-understood, making it difficult to predict and design suitable candidates for this purpose.^{9,10}

Recently, we attached an end-to-end diagonal tether to the conjugated backbones of phenyl-substituted anthracenes to produce a new family of twistacenes, **Ant-Cn**.¹¹ We were thus able to produce helically locked conformations of stable *M* and *P* **Ant-Cn** enantiomers in which the tether prevents the formation of a racemized mixture (by preventing back and forth flipping around the backbone) and the length of the tether controls the degree of backbone twist, while minimizing the effect of side-groups. We found that the twist angle strongly and systematically affects several important properties. Specifically, the larger the twist angle is in **Ant-Cn**, the lower the fluorescence quantum efficiency (Φ_f) and half-life time (τ_f), the smaller the optical band gap, the greater the Cotton effect, and the larger the absorption anisotropy factor.^{12,13} However, the effect of acene twisting on their chemical reactivity remains an open question.¹⁴ Previously, the reactivity of non-planar PAHs was studied with respect to the effect of strain. For example, Bodwell's group demonstrated that the reactivity of bent pyranophanes increases with increasing strain.^{15,16} Houk's group calculated the Diels-Alder reactivity of dienophiles and concluded

that strained dienophiles are more reactive as a result of strain release.¹⁷

Here, we studied the effect of acene twist on $^1\text{O}_2$ capture and release by enantiopure members of the **Ant-Cn** series (Scheme 1). We found that when **Ant-Cn** is both the sensitizer and the diene, the rate of oxygenation depends on the wavelength of irradiation resulting from differences in extinction coefficients. When **Ant-Cn** is not involved in oxygen sensitization, the rate of oxygenation increases with increasing twist. The rate for the release of singlet oxygen show the same trend, and systematically increases with increasing twist. DFT calculations support these findings, as the activation parameters decreases with twist. Switching experiments demonstrated that tethering greatly improves the stability by reducing side reactions.

Scheme 1. Reversible capture and release of $^1\text{O}_2$ by **Ant-Cn**, Ar = 3,5-bis(trifluoromethyl)phenyl.

Chloroform solutions of enantiopure **Ant-Cn** form were subjected to 427 nm or 365 nm irradiation at room temperature. The reaction was followed by UV-vis spectroscopy, with the formation of an absorption band in the 280–300 nm region and

the disappearance of the absorption band in the 330–450 nm region (as exemplified by **Ant-C4** in Figure 1a). The irradiation products were isolated using column chromatography and characterized using ^1H , ^{13}C -NMR, and mass spectrometry. The NMR spectroscopy indicate that the irradiation products, **Ant-C n -O $_2$** , retain the expected C_2 symmetry, with free rotation of the bistrifluoromethylphenyl rings at the NMR timescale. The only significant difference in **Ant-C n -O $_2$** compared with **Ant-C n** is the upfield shift of the carbon at the 9,10 position of anthracene from 135 ppm to 84 ppm as it adopts a tetrahedral configuration (see ESI).

The cycloadducts were recrystallized in hexane/chloroform to yield white needles. X-ray structure of **Ant-C5-O $_2$** revealed a dihedral angle (between the terminal carbons 2-3-6-7 as depicted in Scheme 1) of 16° compared with 7° for its non-tethered analog **Ant-open-O $_2$** . Thus, the tether contributes 9° of the observed twist, while steric hindrance can account for the remaining 7° (Figure 2). It is noteworthy that while **Ant-C5-O $_2$** was crystallized from its racemic mixture, the crystal consists of only one enantiomer, hence it crystallizes as a conglomerate in opposed to the crystal structures of all **Ant-C n** which were found to be racemates.¹¹

P- and *M*- enantiomers of **Ant-C n -O $_2$** which were obtained from the corresponding enantiomers of **Ant-C n** were studied by electronic circular dichroism (ECD) spectroscopy. For the lowest energy transition, the ECD spectra of **Ant-C n -O $_2$** (Figure 1b) display the opposite trend to that previously observed for **Ant-C n** ,¹³ undergoing a hypsochromic shift and decreasing in intensity as the tether shortens.

Figure 1. Absorbance and ECD spectra. (a) Absorbance spectra of the gradual photo-oxidation of **Ant-C4** (blue) irradiated at 427 nm to form **Ant-C4-O $_2$** (green) showing the formation (upward arrow) and disappearance (downward arrows) of bands during photo-oxidation. (b) ECD spectra of the **Ant-C n -O $_2$** series. Dashed line represents the oxidized product of *P*-**Ant-C n** and solid line represents the oxidized product of *M*-**Ant-C n** .

Figure 2. X-ray structure of (a) **Ant-C5-O $_2$** and (b) **Ant-open-O $_2$** . Hydrogens and trifluoromethyl groups are omitted for clarity.

To study the effect of twisting on reactivity, the samples were irradiated at two different wavelengths: 427 nm, which accounts for the π - π^* transition, and for which the extinction coefficient increases with twist (a difference of 70% from **Ant-C6** to **Ant-C3**); and 365 nm, in which the extinction coefficients for **Ant-C5**, **-C4** and **-C3** have similar values (a difference of 5% between **Ant-C5** and **Ant-C3**, while **Ant-C6** is 13% higher than **Ant-C3**, Table S1, see ESI). As portrayed in Figure 3, the rate of photooxidation clearly depends on the wavelength chosen: the rate increases with twist angle at 427 nm whereas it decreases with twist angle at 365 nm. Overall, when **Ant-C n** serves as both the sensitizer and diene, the trend in reactivity can be controlled by the chosen irradiation wavelength.

Figure 3. The change in normalized absorbance of **Ant-C n** at the π - π^* transition upon irradiation at (a) 365 nm and (b) 427 nm.

Several factors can potentially account for the slower rate observed with increased anthracene twisting when irradiated at 365 nm. Since the anthracene serves as both the sensitizer and the diene, the generation of singlet oxygen also needs to be taken into account. In order to separate between the roles of **Ant-C n** as photosensitizer and diene, the reactions were studied with a catalytic amount of methylene blue (MB) sensitizer under irradiation at 617 nm, at which **Ant-C n** does not absorb (Figure S47). We found that the reaction rate increases with increasing twist. This indicates that the trend observed when **Ant-C n** serves as both sensitizer and diene strongly depends on its role as sensitizer, and the rate determining step involves the oxygen sensitization process rather than the cycloaddition.^{18,19}

Previous studies have shown that anthracene can react with oxygen in two competing mechanisms after the first excitation to the S_1 level: a concerted mechanism, involving intersystem crossing (ISC) pathway to form T_1 , which reacts with $^3\text{O}_2$ to form $^1\text{O}_2$, and an electron-transfer to $^3\text{O}_2$ to form radical O_2^- (Scheme 2).^{9, 10, 18, 20} We have previously demonstrated that, as twisting increases, the rate of ISC to the triplet state also increases.²¹ Therefore, it is expected that as the twisting increases, the mechanism which involves ISC will become more dominant. When using MB as the sensitizer, the faster reaction rate with twisting can be explained by the calculated lower energy

for the transition state of twisted **Ant-C3** compared with less-twisted **Ant-C6** as detailed below.

Scheme 2. Possible pathways for oxygen sensitization of **Ant-Cn**.

When heated in the dark, **Ant-Cn-O₂** undergoes cycloreversion, resulting in **Ant-Cn** and singlet oxygen. Switching experiments performed at -5°C for photo-oxidation and 110°C for cycloreversion demonstrated that, after 15 cycles of such irradiation/heating, over 70% of the twistacene remains, indicating its potential as a reversible switch with an average yield of 98% per capture/release cycle (Figure 4, blue). This is in contrast to untethered anthracene, which shows fast decomposition and a slow rate of cycloreversion at 135°C (Figure 4, red). Unlike tethered acenes, the capture and release of $^1\text{O}_2$ by **Ant-Open** results in quick decomposition, with only 42% of the compound remaining after five cycles compared with 81% of **Ant-C4**. The presence of the tether protects the anthracene from overoxidation, and therefore tethered anthracenes are ideal agents for the capture and release of oxygen, functioning as switches.

Figure 4. Top: Switching experiment for **Ant-C4/Ant-C4-O₂** and **Ant-Open/Ant-Open-O₂** in 1,1,2,2-tetrachloroethane under irradiation at 427 nm at -5°C for photo-oxidation and upon heating to 135°C for cycloreversion. Absorbance was measured at 430 and 406 nm for **Ant-Open** and **Ant-C4**, respectively. Bottom: 15 cycles for switching experiment for **Ant-C4/Ant-C4-O₂** heating to 110°C .

The NMR kinetic study revealed that retroDiels-Alder reaction rate increases with increasing twist. For example, at 80°C , the rate increases in more than an order of magnitude from $6.9 \times 10^{-5} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ for **Ant-C6** to $1.1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ for **Ant-C4** (Table S1, see ESI). We investigated the activation parameters for the retroDiels-Alder reaction by expressing the VT-NMR data in Eyring

plots. As can be observed in Figure 5a, ΔG^{\ddagger} decreases from 27.9 kcal/mol for **Ant-C6** to 25.3 kcal/mol for **Ant-C3**. This primarily stems from the decrease in the heat of activation (ΔH^{\ddagger}), despite a decrease in activation entropy (ΔS^{\ddagger}). The retro Diels-Alder reaction was also studied using DFT calculations at the B3LYP/6-31G(d) level of theory. The trend in the free energy of activation is in agreement with the experimental values, with ΔG^{\ddagger} decreasing from 26.3 kcal/mol for **Ant-C6** to 22.4 kcal/mol for **Ant-C3** (Figure 5b).

The HOMO levels of the twistacenes remain almost constant with twist.¹¹ However, examination of the HOMO orbital coefficients of the central carbons (in 9 and 10 positions) in the transition states of **Ant-C6** and **Ant-C3**, reveals an increase of 17% in the sum of the atomic orbital coefficients for **Ant-C3** compared with **Ant-C6** (Table S11 and Figure S59, see ESI).²² This difference can account for the stabilization of the transition state, and consequently for the faster reaction rate observed with increasing twist for both cycloaddition and cycloreversion. We note that strain release can also account for the observed reactivity: As both twisted **Ant-Cn-O₂** and **Ant-Cn** have higher energy as the tether shortens, the activation energy should be smaller, making both the Diels-Alder and the retro Diels-Alder reactions faster with increasing acene twist.

Figure 5. (a) Experimental kinetic parameters of the thermal retro Diels-Alder reaction for different tether lengths (C3-C6 represent propyl to hexyl tethers respectively, in **Ant-Cn-O₂**). (b) Calculated (B3LYP/6-31G(d), in kcal/mol) ΔG^{\ddagger} for retroDiels-Alder of **Ant-C3** (red) and **Ant-C6** (blue).

In summary, we studied the reactivity of twisted anthracene toward photo-oxidation and retro Diels-Alder reactions. We found that reactivity systematically depends on the degree of twisting. The rate of photo-oxidation increases with increasing twist when the twistacene acts as diene, and show dependency on the extinction coefficient when the twistacene acts as both the diene and the sensitizer. The rate of singlet oxygen release by retro Diels-Alder reaction follow a first-order kinetics and increases with increasing twist. The calculated activation parameters are in-line with the experimental values, and the calculated ΔG^\ddagger for **Ant-C3** is lower by 3.9 kcal/mol compared with **Ant-C6**. The reaction, which proceeds under mild conditions, is reversible with an average 98% yield per capture/release cycle, indicating that tethered twistacenes can serve as excellent sources of singlet oxygen.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information

The Supporting Information is available free of charge on the ACS Publications website.

- Experimental procedures; spectral data; X-ray structural data, details of electrochemical measurements and computational details (PDF)
- Cartesian coordinates for optimization (TXT)
- Data for C47H30F12O4 (CIF)
- Data for C44H26F12O4 (CIF)

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Author Contributions

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